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KLYMENCHUKOVA N.S.

Theoretical aspects of the formation of the modus of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship

Relevance of the research topic. *The modern development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy requires constant improvement of the business environment, introduction of progressive changes and revision of regulatory policy through the development of proposals, tools and methods adequate to the current state of the market and the external environment of entrepreneurship. In this context, there is a need to form a mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship.*

Formulation of the problem. *Currently, the system of the national economy lacks a mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship. At the same time, the effective*

development of entrepreneurship and innovation depends on the external environment or institutions represented on the modern market.

Setting goals and objectives of the study – to determine the key aspects of the formation of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship.

Research method or methodology. The theoretical basis of the study was formed by modern methods, namely: dialectical, systematization, observational, monographic.

Presentation of the main material (research results). The key aspects of the formation of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship are determined. The main problems of its development and introduction into the system of the national economy are clarified.

Scope of the results. The conclusions obtained in the scientific research constitute a theoretical platform for improving the development of entrepreneurship and can be used by scientists, entrepreneurs and other market participants.

Conclusions on the article. The key aspects of the formation of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship are proposed. Scientific approaches to its formation and renewal are considered.

Key words: *modus, innovation, external environment, entrepreneurship, resources.*

КЛИМЕНЧУКОВА Н.С.

Теоретичні аспекти формування модусу інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва

Актуальність теми дослідження. Сучасний розвиток підприємництва в інноваційній економіці вимагає постійного удосконалення бізнес–середовища, впровадження прогресивних змін і перегляду регуляторної політики шляхом розробки пропозицій, інструментів та методів адекватних поточному стану ринку та зовнішнього середовища підприємництва. У такому контексті існує потреба формування модусу інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва.

Постановка проблеми. У теперішній час в системі національної економіки відсутній модус інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва. Одночасно ефективний розвиток підприємництва та інновацій залежить від зовнішнього середовища або інституцій представлених на сучасному ринку.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – визначити ключові аспекти формування модусу інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва.

Метод або методологія дослідження. Теоретичне підґрунтя дослідження сформувавали сучасні методи, а саме: діалектичний, систематизації, спостережень, монографічний.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Визначено ключові аспекти формування модусу інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва. З'ясовано основні проблеми його розробки та впровадження в систему національної економіки.

Галузь застосування результатів. Отримані висновки у науковому дослідженні становлять теоретичну платформу для удосконалення розвитку підприємництва та можуть використовуватися науковцями, підприємцями та іншими учасниками ринку.

Висновки за статтею. Запропоновано ключові аспекти формування модусу інституціонального забезпечення розвитку підприємництва. Розглянуто наукові підходи його розробки та оновлення.

Ключові слова: *модус, інновації, зовнішнє середовище, підприємництво, ресурси.*

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The activity of any enterprise is the result of a management process that is not linear and consists of a large number of stages of the production

life cycle, includes a significant number of market stakeholders, organizations, institutions, suppliers, competitors, which introduces a certain degree of risk into the innovative activities of enterprises. According to our vision, if the enterprise

seeks to make profits in the innovative economy, it must undoubtedly be innovatively oriented. In this case, taking into account such multi-objectiveness and multi-subjectivity, there is a need for purposeful management of entrepreneurship with the help of innovative tools, which should be adaptive and modern in accordance with the current challenges of entrepreneurship. There is a need to form a mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship, which would most fully meet the needs of the innovative economy.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, which initiated the solution of this problem and on which the author relies, highlighting previously unsolved parts of the general problem, which is the subject of this article.

The problems of institutional support for the development of innovative activities and entrepreneurship are highlighted in numerous works of scientists [1–13]. At the same time, taking into account the instability of the external environment, the weak state support for innovative activities, the imperfection of infrastructural elements, there is a need to form a mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship, taking into account current problems.

Formulation of the goals of the article (setting the task) – to determine the key aspects of the formation of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results.

Considering the dense interdisciplinary interweaving of scientific theories, concepts, tools, and judgments, the inclusion of the «modus» concept within our research is logical. Entrepreneurship does not function in person within the limits of one science, as an example of economics, public administration or management. The subject of his

study can be found in sociology, psychology, philosophy, mathematics, probability theory, statistics, logic, trade, law. The concept of «modus» (from the Latin *modus* – measure, type, way, image) is used mainly in philosophy. At the same time, this term is also used in other sciences (Table).

According to our understanding, the formation of such a mode in the entrepreneurship system appears as the management of the process of creating innovations due to the improvement of the state of institutional support at the macro level, which enables all interested market stakeholders to obtain specific new results from their activities. Such activities are distributed from suppliers to end users in order to create new value. This process requires creative, creative and coordinated work of all participants in order to effectively use production, financial, technological, human and social resources. Entrepreneurs should be focused on attracting all available resources according to the principle of their optimal use in order to implement effective innovative activities, which will ensure the sustainable growth of the enterprise and the development of business as a system.

The formation of the mode of institutional support in the entrepreneurship system can also be defined as the process of generation, organization and implementation of management methods, tools, structures and mechanisms that are new in the national economy and aimed at improving the institutional matrix of entrepreneurship. In the formation of the modus, the key role belongs to the management at all levels, which is able to develop and implement new business concepts that will lead to the renewal of the business environment. The main tasks of such management at the macro level are:

- application of modern tools for managing the institutional environment;
- coordination of innovative activities of domestic business by defining a unique innovative policy

Definition of the concept «modus» in various sciences

No	Science	Definition
1	Politology	«Modus is the norm»
2	Philosophy	«A mode is a property of an object, inherent in it only in certain states, in contrast to an attribute – an inherent property»
3	Logic	«Modus is a modification of the conclusion of one or another figure of the syllogism depending on the change in the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the premises»
4	Linguistics	«Modus is a method»

Source: summarized by the author from the source [14, p. 778].

adaptive to the external environment, challenges of globalization and world competition;

- determination of the national strategy of innovative development, development of ways, methods and means of its implementation, through determination of operational goals of management and development according to the principle of continuity;
- managing institutional changes inside and, if possible, outside the country in order to best control the current market situation, use the competitive advantages of domestic business and minimize or completely eliminate the negative external impact of factors on entrepreneurship;
- establishing the priority tasks of managing institutional support, the order of their implementation, control and forecasting of expected results;
- drawing up a plan for the necessary financial and investment, technological and technical resources, as well as personnel support necessary for the implementation of state policy in the field of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship;
- providing the state with the necessary resources for new innovation-active enterprises or budget-generating enterprises in order to implement an effective way of doing business, the concept of long-term sustainable development of innovations in conditions of fierce competition and achieving maximum income during a constantly changing institutional environment.

Thus, the management of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship is a complex management process for the creation, improvement and distribution of certain measures of an institutional nature aimed at stimulating innovative activity in the entrepreneurial sector of the economy. Such measures apply to enterprises, institutions and organizations of various forms of ownership, as well as areas of human activity, including science, technology, economy, education and public administration.

In the process of forming the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship, great importance is attached to science and technology. Science is the result of an evolutionary synthesis of accumulated and systematized knowledge in the field of state management of innovations, the analysis of which allows finding the optimal solution for the successful functioning of entrepreneurship in a complex business environment. Technologies

are based on the systematization and implementation of a wide range of tools, skills and management technologies aimed at transforming the institutional framework that will stimulate entrepreneurship to invention and innovation.

Thus, the formation of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship can be considered through the prism of managerial activity, which is characterized by classical components: planning, organization, management, execution, delegation, monitoring and control.

The effectiveness of the development of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship, in our view, depends on the monitoring of the prerequisites for the formation of the foundation for the functioning of business and innovation in our country. We believe that the first stage of business and innovation development covers the period from the independence of our country to 2007–2008. At that time, almost the entire society was full of changes and the desire to build something fundamentally new, which led to the support of innovations and scientific programs that offered new technologies for development of production and provision of services. During this period, society favored private business and innovation as something new and life-changing. The state allocated significant financial resources and encouraged foreign investment in R&D and thus stimulated economic development. The period 1991–2008 was characterized by the expansion of the production of industrial products exclusively due to active technological development, the emergence of innovations in technology, the successful commercialization of know-how and, based on this, the achievement of long-term strategic goals of national development. At the same time, the global financial crisis of 2008 definitely affected entrepreneurship and innovation. Institutional traps as a result of the financial crisis, the imperfection of the market economy, the weak management strategy of enterprises are the main problems of the first generation of business development and innovation.

The second generation of business and innovation development spans the period from 2008 to 2014, which symbolizes the period of gradual exit from the crisis and building up of the country's entrepreneurial and innovative potential. During this period, competition is increasing in the world market of entrepreneurship and innovations, which in-

icates the need for quick orientation of business entities to the production of innovations. At the same time, the lack of venture capital, the weakness of the institutional environment allows entrepreneurship to produce situational, risky or minor innovations that do not have long-term success.

The third generation covers the period from 2014 to the present time. During this period, there is a complete reorientation of the domestic market of entrepreneurship and innovation to European standards in accordance with the needs of wartime. Market conditions put the need to develop innovations in the military, medical, and food industries that provide military needs for certain types of goods on the agenda. In addition to technologization of knowledge, at the expense of state support, the incorporation of science, technology and business is taking place, the logic of connection of the entire innovation process is changing. During this period, the success of the enterprise's innovative activity is achieved due to the exceptionally successful commercialization of innovations on the market with high variability. High risks and significant failures in the institutional matrix are the main threats of the third generation. According to our vision, the tool for solving the problems of the third generation of innovation and business development will be a complete renewal of the institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship, as well as its rapid reformation in accordance with European standards and market needs. During this period, there is a need to ensure greater informativeness of business operations, hedging, use of a significant number of communication channels, with the aim of creating a wide base of customers and suppliers, which can diversify risks in a changing market environment. In this period, there is a need for the emergence of new types of breakthrough innovations focused on consumers, and entrepreneurship must be integrated into the European market.

Conclusions

The above-mentioned periods of the genesis of business and innovation testify to the need to improve state policy, develop adaptive management tools, as well as produce new types of innovations, which is possible under the conditions of the formation of a modern concept of the mode of management of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship. Such a concept should have approaches:

1. The factor approach, which indicates that science, entrepreneurship, resources, technologies, and people are the most important capital for sustainable economic development and security of the country. This approach actualizes the importance of including these factors in managing the mode of institutional provision. By combining these factors, it is possible to achieve the development of new knowledge, its transfer to the sphere of production in order to spread innovations and implement the best entrepreneurial ideas.

2. The functional approach considers the process of managing institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship as a set of functions – planning, organization, management, implementation, delegation, monitoring and control (which we have already mentioned above). The specified management functions should be aimed at the maximum use of the resource and institutional potential of the country in order to realize the positive effects of business management, which is possible under the condition of their professional planning, adjustment and implementation. All the listed functions should be based on taking into account the realistic current state of socio-economic development of the country and entrepreneurship, innovative management tools, and their implementation should be based on the leadership of highly professional managers and public figures, and the involvement of creatively oriented personnel.

3. The systemic approach considers the process of managing the institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship as a complex organizational process with interdependent elements aimed at achieving planned goals. With this approach, the emphasis is not on individual parts of the institutional environment, but on the system as a whole, with the possibility of realizing a synergistic effect. The interdependence of system parts and their joint management, taking into account the changing external and internal environment, leads to multiple effects that allow generating effective innovations, diversifying production and contributing to the creation of new jobs. The application of this approach in the process of managing institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship is a holistic and strategic way of using all parts of the system (input and output), taking into account influencing factors and understanding cause-and-effect relationships. Input elements

of the system represent input data, such as: market conditions, resource environment, behavior of competitors and consumers, current scientific and technological progress.

4. The situational approach shows that various situations or circumstances affect the process of managing institutional support for entrepreneurship development. This approach considers the management process from the social, philosophical, economic, political and technical-technological context (or the action of situational factors) of the development of entrepreneurship and institutions. Their different combination creates unpredictable scenario opportunities that directly affect the formulation of the process of managing the institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship. Timely diagnosis of the trajectory of situational factors makes it possible to analyze the effects of their influence on entrepreneurial institutions and transactional or transformational costs that await business, which allows determining the optimal strategy for optimizing the institutional environment in accordance with the current situation. Quick response of entrepreneurship institutes to situational factors will ensure the success of entrepreneurship in the long term. Implementation of all functions of management of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship should be continuous.

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